

ANIMA

Aviation Noise Impact Management
through Novel Approaches

D6.3 Roadmap Version 1

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¹ Use one of the following codes: R=Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
 DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
 DEC=Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
 OTHER=Software, technical diagram, etc.

² Use one of the following codes: PU=Public, fully open, e.g. web
 CO=Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement
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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	5
2	Available roadmaps	6
2.1	<i>Technology.....</i>	6
2.2	<i>Management of Noise Impact.....</i>	8
2.3	<i>Overall roadmaps</i>	10
3	Development of the new roadmap structure	11
3.1	<i>Subsets.....</i>	11
3.2	<i>Format</i>	12
3.2.1	<i>Data structure</i>	13
3.2.2	<i>High-level roadmap format</i>	15
3.2.3	<i>Topic data sheets</i>	15
3.2.4	<i>Timelines</i>	18
3.3	<i>Definition of maturity level.....</i>	18
4	Release & Update process	20
4.1	<i>Release of V1</i>	20
4.2	<i>Update process.....</i>	21
Annex 1 High-level roadmaps.....		24
Annex 2 Topic datasheets.....		31

1 Introduction

ANIMA Task 6.1 is dedicated to the definition and update of a common strategic research roadmap for aviation noise reduction, involving all key aspects related to mitigation solutions, assessment of noise effects on populations and community engagement.

In the past, strategic research roadmaps have been elaborated, mainly for aircraft noise reduction technology and, more recently, management of aviation noise impact. These roadmaps have been defined and maintained as an essential part of the work of the X-Noise network, funded through subsequent Coordination Actions in FP5, FP6 and FP7. However, in H2020 this network was no longer funded, and the maintenance of the roadmaps was stalled, until some funding became available in ANIMA to resume this work.

The starting point for the new roadmaps is therefore the set of roadmaps available at the end of the last X-Noise project (X-Noise-EV). A new structure of subsets has been developed, together with the design of a new, common, format. Due to the enlarged scope with non-technology related topics, the standard Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scaling has been extended to reflect also the maturity level of these topics.

In ANIMA a scenario-based revision process of the common roadmap is introduced. This process is introduced in this report.

2 Available roadmaps

In the past, strategic research roadmaps have been elaborated, mainly for aircraft noise reduction technology and, more recently, management of aviation noise impact. These roadmaps have been defined and maintained as an essential part of the work of the X-Noise network, funded through subsequent Coordination Actions in FP5, FP6 and FP7.

The latest available set of roadmaps is that, generated within the last X-Noise project (X-Noise-EV), which ended in 2015. This set is included in this section, as it is the starting point of the new common roadmap.

2.1 Technology

A set of 3 technology roadmaps was aimed at the 2020 ACARE SRA1 target (Figures 2-1 to 2-3), whereas a 4th roadmap was delivered, supporting the near term (2015–2025) steps towards the 2035 target, in line with the noise strategy for the new architecture concepts (Figure 2-4).

Figure 2-1. Roadmap for Component/system multi-disciplinary optimisation (2020 target)

Figure 2-2. Roadmap for Adaptive/active flow and noise control (2020 target)

Figure 2-3. Roadmap for Aircraft noise prediction tools (2020 target)

Figure 2-4. Initial combined roadmap (towards 2035 target)

In X-Noise-EV a specific Task Group was active, to identify research priorities for the noise reduction of the small propeller-driven airplanes (General Aviation – GA). Although no dedicated roadmap for GA was delivered, the main topics identified by this Task Group are provided here, in order to be able to initiate such roadmap for inclusion in a future edition of the common strategic roadmap:

- Propeller and engine
- Muffler and exhaust part
- Flying procedures
- Measurement procedures and metrics
- Propagation issues
- Test facilities, experimental data base, mapping
- Identification of sources measurement and analysis
- Noise prediction methodology based on empirical or semi-empirical approach

2.2 Management of Noise Impact

X-Noise-EV was the first project to elaborate a roadmap for research needs in the field of Management of Noise Impact (MNI), based on the following recommendations, made by the AGAPE and OPTI assessments :

- **Consolidate European predictive capability** to evaluate the impacts of aircraft and rotorcraft noise on communities, **including environmental interdependencies**
- Support **improved understanding and modelling** of community impact and overall psycho acoustic **annoyance**.
- Promote a harmonised policy framework on land use practices and mitigation options as well as **develop clear indicators** to assess progress made in their effective implementation.

To support further development of the detailed agenda towards 2035/2050 along the areas identified in the SRIA contribution, a Combined Roadmap for Balanced Approach and Impacts 2010-2025 was developed (Figure 2-5).

Roadmap for Balanced Approach and Impacts 2010-2025

Figure 2-5. Roadmap for Balanced Approach and Impacts (towards 2035 target)

2.3 Overall roadmaps

X-Noise-EV also produced a set of overall roadmaps, to clarify the role of Clean Sky 2 in supporting the last steps towards achievement of the 2020 noise target (Fig.13) as well as the recommended path to address community noise impacts and longer term Generation 3 technology solutions (Figures 2-6 and 2-7).

Figure 2-6. Projects Roadmap towards 2020 Noise Target (-10dB / operation)

Figure 2-7. Contributors Roadmap towards 2035/2050 Noise Target

3 Development of the new roadmap structure

Taking the Contributors roadmap of Figure 2-7 as a basis, a new roadmap structure has been developed, by re-grouping the topics over several logical subsets. In order to arrive at a common strategic research roadmap, a single format for all subsets has been designed, and a scaling similar to the well-known TRL has been defined for the maturity level of all topics.

3.1 Subsets

For the first version of the common strategic roadmap for aviation noise research, 7 subsets have been defined, with each subset part of "Contributors" or Enablers", see Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1 – Subsets of the common strategic roadmap for aviation noise research

Each subset was assigned to a relevant expert within the ANIMA beneficiary organisations, each forming a small task group to identify the research topics to be included in the corresponding subset.

Subset	Subset leader
Technology Development	P. Lempereur (Airbus)
Supersonic Aircraft	S. Lemaire (Dassault)
Airport Noise Management & Indicators	B. Ohlenforst (NLR)
Impacts Understanding	U. Müller/S. Bartels (DLR)
High Fidelity Methods	A. Wilson (ISVR)
Experimental Techniques	F. Cléro (ONERA)
Exposure Tools & Metrics	N. van Oosten (ANOTEC)

In later versions of the common roadmap additional subsets may be included, such as for General Aviation and UAV/UAM, if this is considered appropriate. At present some of the topics relevant to these vehicle groups have been included in the current subsets.

3.2 Format

A new format has been designed, considering especially the following requirements:

- *Ease of maintenance*
The different subsets should be easy to maintain, so updates can be made available without too much effort. Potential future automation of the generation of the roadmaps should be considered.
- *Scalable*
The addition of new topics, an extra level of detail, or an extension of the horizon should be easy to handle.
- *Understandable by wider audience*

The roadmap should be visually attractive and should be understandable for an audience, beyond the current experts, such as policy makers or even the general public. Especially the latter may support the message that the aviation industry assigns significant resources in a well-organised research effort to reduce aviation noise and its impact.

3.2.1 Data structure

As a first step towards the new format, the following common structure for the contents of each roadmap has been defined, at present consisting of 4 levels:

Level	Element	Description	Example
1	Group	High level grouping, related to most relevant organisation type (industry, research centres, etc) – since this has a direct link with the committee that is charged with its maintenance (see section 4)	“Technology Contributors”
2	Subset	Logical grouping as presented in Fig. 3-1	“Technology Development”
3	Topic	Domains within each subset, that form a logical set of elements to be developed	“Low noise airframe design”
4	SubTopic	Particular field of research within a Topic	“Low noise Landing Gear Design and integration”

For each SubTopic several attributes have been defined:

Attribute	Description
Target maturity level at end of period	The maturity level (see section 3.3) that is envisaged to be reached by 2020, 2025, 2030 and 2035
Current status	A short description of historical milestones and the status at which the specific field of research is at at this moment
Vision	A short description of how it is envisaged that this field of research should develop, which milestones have to be considered, and, if applicable, which other fields of research need to be resolved to reach maturity for real world implementation.
Related projects	Past and current EU and national projects that have contributed to the knowledge in this SubTopic and their end date

Although this structure is easily scalable towards even more detailed levels, for this first set of roadmaps it is considered sufficient to elaborate down to SubTopic level. An Excel file was then created and distributed among the subset task groups with the aim to define all elements of each subset (see Figure 3-2).

Roadmap for:	Airport Noise Management		Version: 14/10/2019				Related projects and year
	Topic	Subtopic	Target SRL at end of period				
			2015-2020	2020-2025	2025-2030	2030-2035	
Qualified Balanced Scorecard for QoL		Refine QoL indicators	2-3	3-4	5-6	6-7	<p>Current status</p> <p>Based on literature research a number of indicators has been identified within ANIMA. Those indicators are currently on a global and abstract level. It is not clear yet what exactly the different indicators imply.</p> <p>Vision</p> <p>A comprehensive overview of corresponding measures and factors within each indicator should be worked out. This kind of overview could be some kind of matrix with a large number of factors corresponding to each quality of life indicator. Depending on the development and status of an airport, individual combinations of factors within the different indicators can be used to describe the level of quality of life around airports and areas of development can be identified.</p>
		Making QoL indicators measurable (KPIs)	1	2-3	4-5	6-7	<p>Current status</p> <p>Currently factors describing different QoL indicators in detail are not available.</p> <p>Vision</p> <p>Measurable QoL indicators will grant an additional dimension of information besides dB levels, noise contours and technical recommendations from air traffic control centers. Measurable QoL indicators could be very helpful for decision making processes.</p>
		Comparison/Weighting of QoL	1	2-3	4-5	6-7	<p>Current status</p> <p>There are no guidelines or recommendations available allowing the weighting and comparison of QoL indicators around airports.</p> <p>Vision</p> <p>Weighting of QoL indicators will help to compare the level of QoL for different areas around airports. This can be valuable information for the monitoring of interventions, and the decision making process and the choice of interventions. Weighting and comparing different QoL indicators and corresponding factors should be possible on European level.</p>
		Environmental impact		2-4	5-6	6-7	<p>Current status</p> <p>A qualified balanced scorecard does currently not exist. Typically, the number of highly annoyed or sleep disturbed people or noise contour areas are used to describe the environmental impact of aviation.</p> <p>Vision</p> <p>The environmental impact of aviation should include more global assessment such as the impact of CO2 and NOx. Simultaneously, the local impact of the LTO cycle around airports concerning local air quality should be assessed. A balanced score card should be available for the assessment.</p>

Figure 3-2 – Example Excel sheet with data structure

3.2.2 High-level roadmap format

Based on the information gathered in the Excel sheets elaborated in 3.2.1, a first level of roadmaps has been prepared for each subset with the aim to obtain a visually attractive design, which can be used for dissemination purposes, and at the same time provides a concise overview of the topics and subtopics of each subset. An example of this high-level format is given in Figure 3-3.

Figure 3-3 – Example of a high-level roadmap

3.2.3 Topic data sheets

A second level of roadmaps was then created, consisting of a datasheet for each topic, containing the corresponding subtopics and the additional information on these, also provided in the Excel file:

- Short description of the current status
- A description of the vision how to reach full maturity
- The target maturity levels over time, required to fulfil the vision
- Related projects

Due to the rather detailed information in these datasheets, the target audience will mainly be restricted to direct stakeholders.

An example of such datasheet is presented in Figure 3-4.

High Fidelity Methods		
Noise Generation		
Broadband Aerofoil Response		
Current status	Turbulence generation and broadband acoustic response are usually calculated independently, typically with a partially scale-resolving code to predict the turbulence (previous section) and a linear CAA code for the response.	Projects:
Vision towards final TRL	Increased availability of high performance computing to increase take-up. Development of high order RANS-based methods to reduce cost of acoustic propagation.	
Full System Tone Noise Prediction		
Current status	Tones emanating from components are widely calculated in research and industry using Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) calculations. The number of full system calculations is limited by computational expense.	Projects:
Vision towards final TRL	Increased availability of high performance computing. Development of high order linear CAA codes for internal propagation with complex geometry. Improved models of wall treatments & acoustic liners when not modelled explicitly. In the longer term propagation codes able to model the effect of unsteady mean flows on acoustic propagation and fully coupled codes combining turbulence generation and response.	
Vortex/Blade Interaction		
Current status	These calculations are generally only performed at high fidelity in research programmes due to the computational expense of modelling vortex propagation.	Projects:
Vision towards final TRL	Improved turbulence models for vortex propagation and/or bespoke methods such as vorticity-preserving schemes.	
Combustion & Entropy Noise Sources		
Current status	These noise sources are less well understood, and calculations (typically partially spatially-resolved) are used to help identify source mechanisms.	Projects:
Vision towards final TRL	Further development of multi-physics codes and/or embedded empirical models for unsteady heat release. High quality experimental data at component level (combustor or turbine blade). Accurate source breakdown for validation data at full engine scale. Better source Models for transmission of noise through turbines.	

Figure 3-4 – Example of a topic datasheet

3.2.4 Timelines

As was shown in Section 2, the roadmaps existing at the start of ANIMA mainly presented the envisaged evolution of maturity level of each (sub)topic over time. An additional roadmap exists which highlights the different projects that supported the various topic over the years. The information to derive such roadmaps based on the new structure is already included in the information available. However, the scaling of maturity levels of the non-technology subsets as presented here is preliminary, and further development is likely to be needed (see also 3.3). In addition there exist interrelationships between the (sub)topics within a subset but also between different subsets which still need to be identified and evaluated. Therefore it is considered premature to include at this stage roadmaps in the form of a timeline. An illustration of how such a roadmap may look like is given in Figure 3-5. It is envisaged that an initial full version will be made available in the next issue of the roadmaps.

Figure 3-5 – Example of a roadmap in timeline format

3.3 Definition of maturity level

The development of new technologies and methods requires in most cases a long time to mature. Typically a decade may pass from the first idea upto a full-scale validation under operational conditions, so as to be ready for adoption in real life.

It is therefore necessary to divide the development cycle in several stages, defining successive milestones, representing logical steps towards full maturity.

For technology related research and development, the well-known Technology Readiness Level (TRL) was therefore defined. However, for other domains, usually less related to the development of “hardware”, a common description of the evolution of maturity may be less obvious and probably therefore a common scale has not been adopted.

Since the aim of the present Task in ANIMA is to elaborate a common roadmap for all relevant domains (the subsets), a first attempt is made here to define a common maturity scale for the Enablers (High-Fidelity Methods, Experimental Techniques and Exposure Tools). This scale has been tentatively called “Method Application Level (MAL)”. A very first attempt has also been made to assign a level to each subtopic of the subsets for Impact Understanding and Airport Noise Management. However, at this stage it was found to be too early to converge on a clear description of the various levels of maturity. The objective is to include this in the next issue of the roadmaps.

Figure 3-6 presents the proposed Generic Description of each level, together with the well-known TRL level, used for Technology Development and Supersonic Aircraft. Figure 3-7 provides the initial MAL definition adopted for the Enablers.

Level	Generic description	Technology Development Supersonic Aircraft
1	Basic principles observed and reported	Basic principles observed and reported
2	Concept and/or application formulated	Technology concept and/or application formulated
3	Proof-of-concept	Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof-of-concept
4	Small-scale validation in laboratory environment	Component and/or breadboard validation in laboratory environment
5	Small-scale validation in relevant environment	Component and/or breadboard validation in relevant environment
6	Prototype demonstration in a relevant environment	System/subsystem model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment
7	Prototype demonstration in an operational environment	System prototype demonstration in an operational environment

Figure 3-6 – Generic description and TRL maturity scale for Technology related subsets

Level	High Fidelity Methods	Experimental Techniques Exposure Tools
1	N/A	Basic setup to demonstrate the principle of the method
2	N/A	Demonstration of the method capabilities on simple setup
3	Demonstrated capability of HiFi CFD/CAA method to capture underlying physics.	Validation of the method to characterise simple configurations at small scale with reference data
4	Validation against laboratory / low Reynolds Number experimental data or already validated CFD/CAA results.	Validation of the method to characterise representative geometry at small scale
5	Validation against data from simplified but otherwise representative geometry (e.g. 2D blade section).	Validation of the method on representative component and environment at large scale
6	Validation for a fully representative geometry in a relevant environment at reasonable compute cost.	Validation of the method on representative subsystem model and environment at large scale
7	Wide application within the research community.	Method usable with limited number of parameters and graphic user interface

Figure 3-7 – MAL maturity scale for Enablers subsets

4 Release & Update process

4.1 Release of V1

Once the various subsets of the common research roadmap were elaborated by the corresponding task groups, a validation within WP6 was initiated after which the roadmap was adapted based on the feedback received. The last stage before release of V1 was the consultation with the various ANIMA committees, in which all relevant stakeholders are represented (Figure 4-1).

Figure 4-1 – Process to release roadmap V1

During the second annual meeting, celebrated in September 2019 in Rome, the WP6 validated roadmaps were presented to the three committees for consultation, as indicated in Figure 4-2.

Figure 4-2 – Consultation with committees

The feedback received from the committees was used to update the roadmaps accordingly, and the final set was then presented in the full network meeting on the next day. This gave the committee members a chance to provide further feedback on those subsets not evaluated in their respective committees. This resulted in the final set of roadmaps, constituting V1, as presented in Annex 1 and 2.

4.2 Update process

In ANIMA a scenario-based revision process of the common roadmap is introduced.

To support the work, scenarios are to be defined for technologies, operational procedures and noise management actions for the 2035 and 2050 horizons on a number of selected airports. These scenarios are defined in WP6, will be simulated by the toolkit developed in ANIMA WP4 and results provided back to WP6 for assessment (see Figure 6-1).

Figure 6-1 – Scenario process

The objective of this scenario-based approach is to provide a complete overview of the effect of the planned research and its possibilities of achieving the goals set by ACARE from the standpoint of environmental constraints.

The assessment will need to take into consideration criteria such as noise exposure, annoyance and sleep disturbance and noise-emissions interdependencies. The results of the assessment will be used to inform the update process of the common strategic research roadmap.

A total of two update cycles is planned, each cycle corresponding with the project year in order to take advantage of the WP6 meeting during the half-year progress meeting (March) and the committee meetings and full network meeting to be organised during each annual meeting in September. The various phases of each cycle are indicated in Figure 6-2.

Figure 6-2 – Roadmap update process

Annex 1 High-level roadmaps

Technology Development

Operational Noise Abatement

- Enhanced Arrival Procedures
- Ground operations
- Artificial Intelligence applied to low noise impact flight management

Low noise airframe design

- Low noise Landing Gear Design and integration
- Low noise wing and movables integration

Acoustic integration of unconventional propulsion systems

- Ducted Fan incl. Variable Pitch
- Propellers, Open Rotors & Unducted Fans
- Aeroacoustics of Boundary Layer Ingestions propulsion
- Distributed propulsion
- Propulsion for Urban Air Mobility
- Electric Propulsion system noise

Aero-acoustic integration of UHBR turbofan propulsion system

- Advanced nacelle acoustic technologies
- Advanced flow physics simulation application to fan & turbomachinery
- Integrated low emission combustors
- Aero acoustic scaled demonstration
- Jet / Airframe interaction mitigation

Supersonic Aircraft

Sonic Boom Prediction

- Near&Far-field modelling & validation (cruise)
- Focus Boom modelling & validation
- Far-field prediction model validation using NASA X59

Low Boom Design

- Low boom demonstrator concept study
- Sensitivity effects off-design conditions
- Low LTO & Low boom tradeoffs

Propagation effects

- Atmospheric& Topography effects on Sonic boom
- Indoor propagation
- Secondary boom & other factors

Human Perception and Community Surveys

- Community tests in Europe using X59
- Indoor & Outdoor simulators
- Effect of sonic boom on sleep disturbance

Flight Procedures & Instrumentation

- Relevant Flight Procedures (cruise, focusing)
- Validation of procedures using X59

High Fidelity Methods

Khellil et al AIAA 2017-3012

Turbulence (Precursor to Broadband Noise Generation)

- Turbulence - Wing, Aerofoil or Undercarriage
- Turbulence - Installed Jet & other Installation Sources
- Turbulence Development & Transition

Reboul et al AIAA 2017-3714

Noise Generation

- Broadband Aerofoil Response
- Full System Tone Noise Prediction
- Vortex/Blade Interaction
- Combustion and Entropy Noise Sources

Pestana et al AIAA 2017-3215

Noise Propagation & Radiation

- Blade row transmission, compressor and Turbine Noise
- Acoustic Liner
- Noise/Turbulence Interaction

Shur et al AIAA 2017-3875

Integrated Methods for Prediction and Design Optimisation

- Coupled Source / Propagation
- Coupled Mean flow / Turbulence Generation
- High Fidelity Multi-Disciplinary Design Optimisation

Thomas et al AIAA 2017-3194

New Architecture

- Shielding & Acoustic Installation Effects
- Long Range Propagation
- Ground Noise in an Urban Environment
- Electric Motor Self Noise
- Electric Motor / System Integration

Experimental Techniques

Velocity

- On single points
- In a section
- In the volume
- Time resolved

Density

- Qualitative data in single directions
- Quantitative data in single directions
- Quantitative data in the volume

Pressure

- Dynamic fluctuation on single points
- Mean values on a surface
- Dynamic fluctuations on a surface

Acoustics

- Steady state conditions in free field or anechoic room
- Transient conditions in free field or anechoic room
- In-duct modal detection
- In aerodynamic wind tunnel

Impacts Understanding and Counter Measures

Airport Response

- Improved Communication
- Airport Environmental Management
- Aviation contributions to QoL

Annoyance models

- Acoustical & Non-acoustical factors
 - Fixed wing
 - Multi-modal transport
 - Drones
 - Supersonic aircraft
 - General aviation
 - Helicopters
 - Electric flying (air taxi)

Sleep Models

- Sleep Disturbance
 - Fixed wing
 - Multi-modal transport
 - Supersonic aircraft
 - Electric flying (air taxi)
 - Helicopters
 - General aviation
 - Drones

Health Models

- Adults & Children
 - Fixed wing
 - Multi-modal transport
 - General aviation
 - Electric flying (air taxi)
 - Drones
 - Helicopters
 - Supersonic aircraft

Airport Noise Management & Indicators

Measurable Benefits of interventions of Land-Use planning

- Policy measures
- Noise reduction measures
- Noise masking measures
- Adaptive land-use planning
- Harmonization of European Land-Use planning measures

Community Engagement Strategy

- Information
- Empowerment
- Engage communities with airport decisions

Qualified Balanced Scorecard for QoL

- Refine QoL indicators
- Making QoL indicators measurable (KPIs)
- Comparison/Weighting of QoL
- Environmental impact

Exposure Tools & Metrics

Noise Exposure Models

- Improvements of Integrated Models
- Semi-empirical source noise models for conventional and future aircraft/powerplant
- Propagation models
- Cruise noise models

Impact models

- Virtual Resident
- Acoustical factors
- Non-acoustical factors

Audiovisual simulations

- Audio simulation tools
- Visualization tools

Interdependencies

- Noise vs. Fuel/CO2
- Noise vs. LAQ (NOx, PM,..)
- Noise vs. 3rd Party Risk

Metrics

- Acoustic metrics
- Impact indicators
- Land Use Planning indicators
- Interdependencies metric
- Metrics for Communication
- Monetisation

Annex 2 Topic datasheets

Topic datasheets are confidential (available to certain parties on request). It is noted that for several (sub)topics not all information is included. This is mainly due to the fact that for these (sub)topics no consensus has been reached yet within the corresponding task group. The datasheets will be updated as soon as this information becomes available.

These datasheets are available in Excel format.